

3D Printers' Impact on the Future of Construction

Amirhossein JavaheriKhah¹, Mercedes Valiente Lopez², Miguel Fernandez Alvarez³

¹Ph.D. Student, amirhossein.javaheri@alumnos.upm.es

²Full Professor of Architectural Drawing. mercedes.valiente@upm.es

³Professor at the Higher Technical School of Edification upm m.fernandez@upm.es

Abstract

One of the most comprehensive technologies in the world is a three-dimensional printing technology used in different areas. The three-dimensional print can become one of the buildings of the building. With this method, the cost of building materials will be dramatically reduced, because, in this method, fewer materials are used and even wasted, it is also likely that human mistakes are almost zero. By replacing these giant robots instead of manpower, as well as the replacement of recycled materials and waste, instead of new materials, it can be claimed that the construction industry has taken a major step toward achieving its goals. The purpose of this research is to investigate the role and performance of 3D printers in the construction industry and review the benefits and disadvantages of this technology. This research has been relying on a descriptive method and refers to many valid articles and library studies.

Keywords: 3D printer, Construction, Technology, Building, Material

1 INTRODUCTION

The construction industry has an annual revenue of nearly 10 trillion USD, which represents around 6% of the global GDP. Indeed, the engineering and construction industry is a cornerstone of the world's economy [1]. Construction companies are always seeking new means to increase productivity while reducing costs [2]. Studies have shown that over the years, labor productivity in the construction industry has been declining [3]. The lack of implementation of new technology is one of the reason of this decline [4]. Additive Manufacturing (AM), or more commonly 3D printing, is one of the newest system of technology that has been introduced in the construction industry. Some drivers are pushing construction towards automation: lowering labor for safety reasons; reducing construction time on-site; reducing production costs; and/or increasing architectural freedom [5]. You can see in Figure 1, construction is done using 3D printers without the need for a worker and only with an operator and a robot .

Figure 1. Construction with 3D printers (Source : www.edelplast.com/3Dprinter)

Additionally, 3D printing helps address sustainability issues. The construction industry has been recognized as one industry that consumes a considerable amount of resources and poses significant environmental stresses [6]. 3D printing of buildings is a new technology for building sustainable buildings and houses of the future. A new construction method began with the invention of the 3D printer. The first 3D printer was invented by Charles Hall in 1984, and 3D printing became one of the The fastest system. It was very complicated and expensive at first, but over time, 3D printing became part of everyday life, and printers entered all industries. In 2014, the real revolution in the construction industry began with the printing of the first house and a new chapter in construction technology began. This paper investigates briefly the different 3D printing systems in construction, their benefits, and the challenges associated with their use in construction projects. The use of 3D printing technology offers several advantages over traditional methods. However, additional challenges and risks are faced due to the introduction of this new technology in construction projects.

2 3D Concrete Printing Method

In order for a structure to be printed in 3D, a model using special modeling software such as SAP. Rhaino-Maya-Zbrush and etc. Design or scan a prefabricated model. In 3D printing of buildings, printers

are a kind of robot and are driven by a computer [8]. In some cases, due to the high cost or unavailability of a special type of 3D scanner, the Kinect device made by Microsoft will be used in the initial stage. Then we have a digital model that we divide into 2D sections and do the printing process layer by layer [9]. This technology reduces construction costs by 40 to 50 percent for the production of more complex structures without the need for structures. Carbon production can be significantly reduced during mass production by 3D printers [10]. In Figure 2, the 3D printer is making the desired design using concrete materials.

Figure 2. Construction with 3D printers with concrete (Source: Austin, Lim & Le, 2012)

3 3D Printing Features

3.1 Reduction of construction waste and its impact on the environment;

3.2 Its ability to create free form shapes reduces costs;

3.3 The cost of a house built with this technology mainly depends on the items used and the working time of the machine. Innovative structures may cost even less than rectangular structures because they require less support.

3.4 Gives architects more flexibility in design because it eliminates many design constraints

4 types of 3D Printing

There are different types of 3D printing technology that process different materials in different ways.

Now for Prototyping and industrial production:

Functional plastics, Metals (gold, bronze, platinum ...), ceramic, Sand

Used to create the final object. Different types of 3D printers each use different materials. Some of these technologies used in construction are:

4.1 SLS

One of the techniques for 3D printing is selecting a laser spray (SLS), which involves using a laser to melt material particles together to create an object, and a laser is used to bake a liquid resin and turn it into hard plastic. Used in SLS technology, they usually have high strength and flexibility, the most popular of which are nylon and polystyrene [11]. Figure 3 shows the process of using a 3D printer with the SLS method.

Figure 3. 3D printer SLS (Source: Avanish Kumar Srivastava, 2021)

4.2 FDM

Sediment modeling is a technology that was invented in 1988 by Scott Crump. Flexible materials that harden themselves during the cooling process are extruded through a double-sided nozzle. Modeling and materials are stored based on cross-sections, produced from a digital model supported by a printer. The nozzle consists of resistive vapors that hold the filament at a suitable melting point that can easily flow through the nozzle to form layers. Like other technologies, after creating one layer, one platform is reduced and the next layer is created. This process is repeated until the whole process is complete. [12]. In Figure 4, you can see that the device is making a design using spool material.

Figure 4. 3D printer FDM (Source: Avanish Kumar Srivastava, 2021)

4.3 Contour Crafting

It is a construction technology used in 2006 by Behrokh Khoshnouis of the University of California, Science Information Institute, which uses a crane or computer crane to produce buildings quickly,

efficiently, and with little manual labor. Contour crafting technology reduces the additive manufacturing process from the manufacture of small industrial parts to the construction of buildings. It is an add-on technology that uses computer control to exploit it. Contour crafting gives the ability to make thick layers using different materials without compromising the quality of the surface. The inventor's idea is to create a printer that has one or more nozzles mounted in two parallel lines at the construction site. The next part of the process is similar to the previous processes and the materials are extruded through the nozzle and placed in the form of empty blocks [13.] The purpose of contour crafting is to build custom houses in a short time of one day. Craft contouring differs from other methods in dimensions, projects made with craft contouring have larger dimensions and implementation restrictions are less than SLS and FDM methods. In Figure 5, using the contour crafting method, which is one of the most common methods, you can build a house without the need for workers and reduce construction time and construction hazards.

Figure 5. Construction of the Building by contour crafting (Source: Enzo Vergara, 2014)

4.3.1 Application of contour crafting

Since contour crafting has the potential to significantly reduce costs and is environmentally friendly, it can be used effectively to build homes for the low-income class and shelter for victims of disasters and even colonies in remote areas or on other planets. Complex structures can also be constructed. The main advantages provided by the calligrapher are that the process, which is mainly done by the machine, will be safer and its cost and time will be reduced by using suitable materials and with good printer parameters. In addition, 3D printing can create large components with unlimited architectural flexibility and the highest accuracy [13].

5 Benefits of 3D printing

Based on the literature review, the main benefits are time, cost, geometric freedom, sustainability, and safety. 3D printing allows to reduce the construction time considerably. Faster construction is the most cited benefit of 3D printing. Reduction of construction costs is also cited as the main benefit. The labor cost of this office, in Dubai, was 60% lower than traditional buildings of the same size. 3D printing also improves productivity which results in cost savings. AM is seen as a way of addressing construction productivity challenges. Using 3D printing technology allows more geometric freedom to design structures that are not otherwise possible. Geometric freedom is often cited as one of the main benefits. Sustainability is the main benefit of 3D printing. 3D printing allows for the design and construction of eco-friendly structures. Using 3D printing reduces waste produced during construction and also reduces formwork. The printing process will eliminate unnecessary waste of materials, thus reducing the

environmental impacts of the production/construction process Reducing the use of formwork reduces the amount of wood and therefore trees. The new technology also improves safety on construction sites. 3D printing results in safer sites. 3D printing reduces the number of injuries and fatalities on site as the printers will be able to do most of the hazardous and dangerous work. [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [16], [18], [19], [21], [23].

6 Limitations

Despite the many advantages of 3D printing, this technology has its limitations and disadvantages. Labor use is minimized and employment conditions are reduced. It is difficult to imagine that 3D printing will replace traditional construction, and it is more likely that the two will be present together in the industry. 3D printing may be associated with and support traditional techniques. In this method, the use of the software is essential. 3D printing can only do up to a certain size and has limitations in dimensions and size. All of this limits the building's 3D printing technology.

7 Prototype testing and validation for performance standards

In this section, a study of structures made by printers is performed to evaluate cycle by cycle. The production of additives by printers is different from conventional methods because the performance of objects is based on the direction of the layer and their size. This means testing the required properties of structures with building standards and codes. Load-bearing capacity is the most important and obvious factor that guarantees structural performance and is one of the key criteria [24]. Free structures and figure made to measure density, tensile strength, and compressive strength in different directions are examined [25]. They tested the strength and stress capacity of concrete under different conditions. Apart from load-bearing, other features such as durability, resistance to water vapor emission, thermal properties, and fire resistance are important aspects for use in the construction industry. [26.] The challenges of using 3D printing are:

- Structural performance and the need for steel to improve tensile strength and mobility
- Matters related to micrometry and fluidity of cement mixture (pumping problem)
- Hardening and connection of concrete layers and bonding between layers [27]

Table 1. performance standards

substance	The ratio of mixtures (kg/m ³)				
	Mixed1	Mixed2	Mixed3	Mixed4	Mixed
Sand	1612	1485	1362	1241	1123
Cement	376	446	513	579	643
Fly ash	107	127	147	165	184
Silica fume	54	64	73	83	92
water	150	178	205	232	257

8 3D printing cost analysis and life cycle evaluation

Large-scale production of additives is a very expensive process due to initial adjustment costs and required materials. But with this technology, about 50% of costs such as scaffolding, etc. Several studies have compared the cost of traditional manufacturing methods with printers. These studies show that the cost of building a 5 by 3-meter wall with the help of a printer is almost half that of traditional construction. There are various costs associated with the manufacture of concrete, mainly the labor force and the materials and equipment required by this department to analyze. Formatting alone accounts for 28 to 50 percent of the cost. The table below shows the amount of labor, raw materials, and equipment required for different types of walls [28].

Table 2. cost analysis and life cycle evaluation

Construction method	Types of costs		
	workforce	Raw material	Equipment
Straight wall / conventional method	56%	23%	21%
Straight wall / printer	36%	45%	18%
Curved wall / conventional method	22%	75%	3%
Curved wall / printer	38%	44%	18%

9 Conclusion

The advent of 3D printing in the construction industry has transformed many new projects. 3D printers are coming together to make significant strides in building and developing the right materials. Studies show that 3D printing is effectively regarded as one with lower costs and environmental benefits. Although we are currently at the beginning of this new technology, with the passage of time and optimization of performance and cost of initial construction, we can use this method as one of the conventional methods in the construction industry in the Later years. Finally, despite the many advances in 3D printing of buildings and the construction of suitable materials, this method alone is able to meet all needs. It is not construction, so it is difficult to imagine that 3D printing will replace traditional construction, and it is more likely that the two will be present in the industry together. 3D printing may be like strong backing with and supporting traditional techniques. Also For construction 3Dp methods to be successful in the future there must be an ability for all the processes involved to be able to be performed on site with little to no effect of the everyday outdoor conditions of building sites. An additional issue is that with equipment involving robotic workers, the technology should be easy to use and have intuitive user interfaces and be able to share work spaces with workers as well as encompass a high level of safety (Vähä, 2013). Without such functionality, it seems likely to present day observers that automated construction 3Dp will not be in widespread use for many years to come.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Gerbert, S. Castagnino, C. Rothballer, A. Renz, R. Filitz. (2016). The transformative power of building information modeling, March 08, 2016, Boston Consulting Group, [Online]. Available: <https://www.bcgperspectives.com/content/articles/engineered-products-project-business-digital-engineering-construction/>, [Accessed 28 Jan. 2019].
- [2] S. El-Sayegh, L. Romdhane, and S. Manjikian, (2020). A critical review of 3D printing in construction: benefits, challenges, and risks. *Archiv.Civ. Mech.Eng* 20, 34. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43452-020-00038-w>
- [3] T. Bock, "The future of construction automation: Technological disruption and the upcoming ubiquity of robotics," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 59, pp. 113-121, 2015.
- [4] B. García de Soto, I. Agustí-Juan, J. Hunhevicz, S. Joss, K. Graser, G. Habert, B. Adey, "Productivity of digital fabrication in construction: Cost and time analysis of a robotically built wall," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 92, pp. 297-311, 2018.
- [5] S. Lim, R. A. Buswell, R. A. Le, Austin, A. G. F. Gibb, T. Thorpe, "Developments in construction-scale additive manufacturing processes," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 21, pp. 172–268, 2011.
- [6] P. Wu, J. Wang, and X. Wang, "A critical review of the use of 3D printing in the construction industry," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 68, pp. 21-31, 2016.
- [7] Hager A et al. 3D printing of buildings and building components as the future of sustainable construction? , *Procedia Engineering*; 151: 292-299, 2016.
- [8] Gosselin, C, Duballet, R, Roux, P, Gaudilliere, N, Dirrenberger, J, Morel, P 2016,
- [9] Large-scale 3D printing of ultra-high performance concrete – a new processing route for architects and builders', *Materials & Design*, Vol 100, June 2016.
- [10] Karyne, L 2014, A Chinese Company 3D Printed 10 Houses in A Day, *Business Insider*, viewed 27th September 2018,>.
- [11] Sakin M, Caner Kiroglu Y. 3D Printing of Buildings: Construction of the Sustainable Houses of the Future by BIM, *Procedia Engineering*; 134: 702-711, 2017.
- [12] Xia M, Sanjayan J. Method of formulating geopolymers for 3D printing for construction applications, *material, and design*; 110: 382-390, 2016.
- [13] Zhang J. Contour Crafting process planning and optimization, 2009.
- [14] S. El-Sayegh, L. Romdhane, and S. Manjikian, (2020). A critical review of 3D printing in construction: benefits, challenges, and risks. *Archiv.Civ. Mech.Eng* 20, 34. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43452-020-00038-w>

- [15] I. Hager, A. Golonka, and R. Putanowicz, "3D printing of buildings and building components as the future of sustainable construction?" *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 151, pp. 292-299, 2016.
- [16] O. Davtalab, A. Kazemian, and B. Khoshnevis, "Perspectives on a bim-integrated software platform for robotic construction through contour crafting," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 89, pp. 13-23, 2018.
- [17] S. Lim, R. A. Buswell, R. A. Le, Austin, A. G. F. Gibb, T. Thorpe, "Developments in construction-scale additive manufacturing processes," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 21, pp. 262–268, 2011.
- [18] P. Wu, J. Wang, and X. Wang, "A critical review of the use of 3D printing in the construction industry," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 68, pp. 21-31, 2016.
- [19] S. Ghaffar, J. Corker, M. Fan, "Additive manufacturing technology and its implementation in construction as an eco-innovative solution," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 93, pp. 1-11, 2018.
- [20] Apis Cor. We Print Buildings, Retrieved from: APIs-cor.com/en/.
- [21] I. Kothman and N. Faber, "How 3D printing technology changes the rules of the game," *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, vol. 27, no. 7, pp. 932-943, 2016.
- [22] M. A. Kreiger, B. A. MacAllister, J. M. Wilhoit, M. P. Case, "The current state of 3D printing for use in construction," in *Proc. the 2015 Conference on Autonomous and Robotic Construction of Infrastructure*, Ames, Iowa, pp. 149-158, 2015
- [23] L. Robichaud and V. S. Anantatmula, "Greening project management practices for sustainable construction," *Journal of Management in Engineering*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 48-57, 2011.
- [24] De Schutter, G, Lesage, K, Mechtcherine, V, Naidu Neralla, V, Habert, G, Agusti-Juan, I 2018, 'Vision of 3D printing with concrete – Technical, economic and environmental potentials', *Cement and Concrete Research*, Vol. 112, October 2018, Pg. 25 – 36.
- [25] Buchanan, A, Honey, B 1994, Energy and carbon dioxide implications of building construction, *Energy and Buildings*, Vol. 20, November 2013, Pg. 205 – 217, viewed 10th September 2018.
- [26] Nassen, J, Holmberg, J, Wadeskog, A, Nyman, M 2007, 'Direct and indirect energy use and carbon emissions in the production phase of buildings: An input-output analysis', *Energy*, Vol. 32, Issue 9, September 2007, Pg. 1593 – 1602, viewed 10th September 2018,
- [27] Berndt, M 2009, 'Properties of sustainable concrete containing fly ash, slag and recycled concrete aggregate', *Construction and Building Materials*, Vol. 23, Issue 7, July 2009, Pg. 2606 – 2613.
- [28] Labonnote, N, Rønning, A, Manum, B & Rütther, P 2016, "Additive construction: State-of-the-art, challenges and opportunities", *Automation in Construction*, vol. 72, pp. 347-366.